

Rac-4o

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-160-1-rac-10%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	88	Acq. Method Set:	10% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 160 1 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/23/2022 3:35:53 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/20/2022 11:31:16 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	14.093	2067758	49.98	85083
2	18.733	2069812	50.02	

Asy-4o

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-160-1-asy-10%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	14	Acq. Method Set:	10% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	xt 3 160 1 asy
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/24/2022 11:08:41 AM CST		
Date Processed:	10/20/2022 11:29:15 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	14.597	8978001	96.41	363494
2	19.436	334362	3.59	10883